

Job Passion and its Role in the Promotion of Green Innovation an Analytical Study of the Views of a Selected Sample of Employees at Noor Al Kafeel Company

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Abstract: The research aims to analyze and understand the relationship between the independent variable, (job passion) with its dimensions (harmonious passion and obsessive passion) and the dependent variable (Green Innovation) with its dimensions (green design, green operations) from The problem was represented by the following question (What is the relationship between job passion and creative performance) and the importance of the clear role in enhancing Green Innovation was clarified and the research sample was represented by (164) respondents from employees as a community of (270) employees / Noor Al Kafeel Company by adopting the questionnaire form and using statistical tools including linear regression and correlation coefficient and a set of conclusions were obtained including (the existence of a major role for job passion in enhancing Green Innovation, meaning that the more awareness of job passion among employees in Noor Al Kafeel Company increases through employees' awareness of the existence of feelings of love and satisfaction in their work, the existence of self-identity in their work, and their feeling of enjoyment in their work, in addition to their awareness that their work enhances the possibility of contributing to decision-making, the more this leads to enhancing creativity Green) While the recommendations were (promoting values that encourage innovation and environmental protection, such as responsibility, cooperation, respect, critical thinking, and communicating effectively with employees about the importance of sustainability and the environmental achievements of the company).

Keywords: Job passion, Green Innovation, Noor Al-Kafeel Company / Al-Abbas's Holy Shrine / Karbala / Iraq.

Introduction:

There is currently a significant global trend towards sustainability and environmental consciousness, prompting corporations to actively pursue the implementation of eco-friendly practices. Within this framework, the function of human resources plays a significant role in driving the transformation of organizational culture and fostering employee creativity and innovation in the realm of sustainability. Noor Al-Kafeel Company, exemplifying this, plays a significant role in this domain by striving to bolster the notion of Green Innovation through investment in its personnel and their enthusiasm for their work.

Job passion refers to the intense enthusiasm and motivation that an individual experiences towards their work. It plays a significant role in enhancing productivity and fostering innovation. When a person possesses a strong sense of passion for their profession, they exhibit a greater willingness to offer novel ideas and inventive solutions to the company's difficulties. Within the

realm of Green Innovation, employee enthusiasm can motivate individuals to actively seek out novel methods to enhance the company's ecological impact and create products and services that are environmentally sustainable.

Green Innovation refers to the capacity to produce novel ideas and inventive solutions that aid in safeguarding the environment and enhancing the environmental efficacy of businesses. It is widely acknowledged as a crucial component in attaining sustainable development. At Noon Al Kafeel, Green Innovation may be demonstrated in various domains, including the development of eco-friendly products, enhancement of energy and water efficiency, waste reduction, and more.

In this context, the function of human resources is to develop and execute initiatives and regulations with the goal of fostering employees' enthusiasm for their work and promoting their creativity in the realm of sustainability. This can be accomplished by creating a work atmosphere that fosters inspiration, implementing targeted training programs, equipping employees with the essential resources for creativity, and recognizing and valuing the contributions of innovative staff members.

The research comprised four chapters. The first chapter focused on the methodology, the second chapter discussed the theoretical aspect, and the third chapter addressed the practical aspect. The research concluded with the fourth chapter, which presented the conclusions and recommendations based on the statistical analysis.

1- Research Methodology

The section deals with the problem, objectives, importance, research methodology, information collection tools, analysis, and statistical processing as follows: -

1-1- Research problem: Given the information provided regarding the weakness of Green Innovation at Noor Al-Kafeel Company in Karbala and its correlation with the weakness of job passion behaviors among human resources, what is the extent to which the weakness of job passion among employees of Noon Al-Kafeel Company in Karbala contributes to their weakness in Green Innovation? Also, what is the causal relationship between these two variables?

"The environmental performance of Noor Al-Kafeel Company in Karbala is adversely affected by the employees' lack of job passion and Green Innovation. The objective of this investigation is to ascertain the correlation between a lack of job passion and a low level of Green Innovation among employees, as well as to identify additional factors that contribute to this issue. The research also aims to suggest practical solutions that will improve the company's environmental performance and increase job passion and Green Innovation.

1-2- Research objectives are manifested in the following: -

- 1- Identifying the level of awareness of employees at the studied company of the main study variables.
- 2- Revealing the level of correlation and influence between job passion and Green Innovation.
- 3- Providing a set of recommendations that contribute to the company's success within these two variables.

1-3- Importance of the research: Importance is represented by the following: -

1. A deeper understanding of the relationship: The research helps reveal the precise relationship between job passion and Green Innovation and how each affects the other.
2. Developing new theories: The research may contribute to developing new theories about Green Innovation and job passion in the work environment.

3. Providing practical solutions: The research can provide practical solutions to enhance job passion and Green Innovation in Noor Al Kafeel Company and other companies.
4. Evaluating programs and initiatives: The research can be used to evaluate the effectiveness of programs and initiatives that aim to enhance sustainability and creativity in companies.
5. Generalizing the results: The research results can be generalized to other companies in different sectors, which contributes to spreading the culture of sustainability and creativity.

1-4- Hypothetical model

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on scientific literature.

1-5- Research hypotheses:

Are as follows: -

1- (H1) There is a strong effect between the independent variable, career passion, and the dependent variable, Green Innovation.

The following two secondary hypotheses branch out from it:

- (H1-1) There is a strong effect between the variable, harmonious passion, and the dependent variable, Green Innovation
- (H1-2) There is a strong effect between the variable, obsessive passion, and the dependent variable, Green Innovation

1-6- A General Overview of Noor Al-Kafeel Company in Karbala Governorate

Noor Al-Kafeel Company is one of the companies affiliated with the Al-Abbas's Holy Shrine in the holy city of Karbala. The company was established with the aim of providing high-quality services to the Iraqi community, providing job opportunities for young people, and contributing to the country's economic development.

1- Company objectives:

- Providing high-quality food products: The company focuses on producing and distributing a wide range of food products, including meat, dairy, and other food products, at competitive prices and high quality.
- Supporting the national economy: The company seeks to support the national economy by investing in local industries and providing job opportunities for citizens.
- Community Service: The company is committed to serving the local community and meeting its needs by providing safe and healthy food products.
- Expansion and Growth: The company seeks to expand in its local and regional markets and enhance its position as one of the leading companies in the food industry in Iraq.

2- Company Services:

In addition to producing and distributing food products, Noor Al Kafeel Company provides a range of other services, such as:

- **Distribution:** The company has a wide distribution network covering various regions of Iraq, ensuring that its products reach consumers easily.
- **Marketing:** The company markets its products through various marketing channels, including its branches and supermarkets.
- **Customer Service:** The company provides distinguished customer service to respond to customer inquiries and solve their problems.

1-7- Demographic factors of the study sample and response rate

The researcher personally gave 170 surveys to a random group of employees from Noor Al Kafeel Company to make sure the sample accurately and sufficiently represented the study population. Following the retrieval of (168) questionnaires, it was discovered that (164) questionnaires with a 96% response rate were valid for statistical analysis. This is a sufficient number based on the statistical table (Krejcie, 1970: 608), which indicates that since the community is 270 individuals, the sufficient number to represent this community is at least 160 individuals.

The study sample obtained different characteristics, whether in terms of personal or professional characteristics, which were represented by) age, human type, educational qualification, and years of service, as shown in the table below:

Table (2) Personal information of the study sample

the age	Recurrence	%
18 - 30 years	39	23.78%
31 - 40 years	37	22.56%
41 - 50 years	31	18.90%
51 years and more	57	34.76%
Total	164	100

Gender	Recurrence	%
Male	133	81.10%
Female	31	18.90%
Total	164	100

Educational Qualification	Recurrence	%
Intermediate	11	7%
Preparatory	19	12%
Bachelor's	113	69%
Other	21	13%
Total	164	100

Number of years of experience	Recurrence	%
18 - 30 years	39	23.78%
31 - 40 years	37	22.56%
41 - 50 years	31	18.90%
51 years and more	57	34.76%
Total	164	100

Five years or less	25	15.24%
6 to 10 years	19	11.59%
11 to 15 years	31	18.90%
16 to 20 years	44	26.83%
20 and more	45	27.44%
Total	164	100

Table 1 indicates the age of the sample individuals, showing that the age group (from 18 to 30 years) under study represented (23.78%), while the group (from 31 to 40 years) represented (22.56%) of the total sample individuals. The age indicator for the individuals indicates that most of them were from the youth energies under study, and this is a good indicator indicating that the questionnaire was not limited to one age group without others, as the opinions of workers at different age levels were obtained. As the table above indicates the educational attainment of the respondents, it was shown that (113, 19, and 11) qualify (bachelor's, preparatory, intermediate) respectively, and thus they can understand the components of the questionnaire and deal with it properly. The table indicates the length of service of the individuals surveyed, as it shows that (19, 31, 44, 45) of the individuals surveyed have service (from 6 to 10 years, from 11 to 15 years, 16 to 20 years, 20 or more) respectively in the company studied. These are years during which workers acquire knowledge and experience in how to deal with the problems they face at work and make appropriate decisions regarding them.

1-8- The study's testing tool's validity and dependability, as well as its normal distribution:

When we talk about reliability, we are referring to the guarantee that the answer will remain the same in the case that the instrument is re-applied to the same sample at a different time. Additionally, Reliability pertains to the magnitude of the study's scope and the consistency of the findings. The steadiness of the scale might vary from zero to the accurate value, and the consistency of the scale is increased in proportion to the degree to which the value of the stability coefficient is closer to the correct one. Using Cronbach's alpha, According to studies, a value greater than 70% is considered acceptable for statistical acceptance in studies on administration and behavior (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994), the stability coefficient was utilized. Cronbach's alpha was employed. When it comes to the credibility criterion, it demonstrates that the paragraphs in question are capable of measuring the primary aim for which they were designed and that they are acceptable with values that are higher than 70%. In order to determine whether or not the data The skewness and kurtosis factors will be used to look at data that has a normal distribution. This will help figure out what kind of test will work best with the data that was collected. "The skewness and kurtosis coefficients don't have a set value that shows which is the highest or lowest.", " according to Wegner (2013): 83. However, there is an approximate formula that can be adopted, which states that the values of both kurtosis and kurtosis between (1.96: -1.96) are the numbers that make the data behave normally?. This formula can be adopted. In light of this, the concepts proposed by the researcher, Wegner, were taken into consideration.

Table (2) " The normal distribution and the research scale's coefficient of validity and reliability "

	Number of phrases	stability coefficient	reliability coefficient	Skewness	Kurtosis
Harmonious Passion	5	89.40%	94.55%	0.664	-1.577
Obsessive Passion	5	87.40%	93.49%	0.781	1.204

Functional Passion	10	%88.40	94.02%	0.767	-1.167
Green Design	7	92.60%	96.23%	0.711	-1.067
Green Operations	7	90.40%	95.08%	0.853	1.163
Green innovation	14	%91.50	95.66%	1.214	-1.577

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The table above shows the following: -

- The application of the test made it abundantly evident that all of the axes, both individually and together, produced results that were satisfactory, as demonstrated.
- All values of the skewness and flatness coefficients fell within a range between (1.96: -1.96), so all paragraphs of the study variables and their dimensions are distributed normally.

2- Theoretical aspect

2-1- Job passion.

- 1- **Concept:** (Vallerand & Houliort 2019: 56) indicated that it is the strong desire shown by the working individual towards an activity or work that achieves his self and identity and for which he expends his energies, experiences, and time and regularly interacts around completing the work. (Fu, et al, 2020: 47) indicated that it represents the feelings, attitudes, and tendencies of the working individual towards a specific job or activity with all love, desire, and passion, and he seeks to complete the work with high energy and feelings of pride.
- 2- **Importance:** (Pollack et al., 2020: 317) show that importance is that it represents the key to developing performance and enhances the ability of individuals to achieve goals. It also contributes to helping the organization excel and succeed in a highly complex and changing environment and provides organizational success and job satisfaction, which provide happiness to individuals and organizational loyalty to the organization. Explain (Tolentino et al., 2022: 17) Importance is embodied through the possibility of identifying many positive results that contribute to the success of the organization, such as organizational behavior, institutional commitment, job satisfaction, improving the psychological state of the working individual, and deepening the cohesive job connection, all of which lead to success.
- 3- **Dimensions:** The dimensions mentioned by (Fu et al., 2022, 28) were adopted, which are (harmonious passion and obsessive passion), and we will discuss this according to the following:
 - A- **Harmonious passion:** (Birkeland & Buch 2015: 398) explained that it is the emotional tendency of the individual toward his work, as it is considered important and enjoyable and is part of his self-identity and gives the individual improved performance, empowerment, and increased well-being in addition to commitment and loyalty and works to achieve the desires and needs of the individual and improves the performance and quality of the organization. (Ho, et al, 2021: 133) added that it represents the desire of the individual towards work and is characterized by intensity, love, and respect for work with the positive feelings represented by the value and importance of the work he performs, which makes him more committed voluntarily without any pressures and this gives him experience and knowledge.
 - B- **Obsessive Passion:** It was referred to by (Pathak & Srivastava, 2020: 328) as the individual's continuous work in a specific activity to which he devotes most of his time, so he feels that work has taken over most of his time and controls it, and dominates it as it exploits most of the individual's abilities and capabilities greatly, so it is closely linked to the individual's life.

(Newman et al., 2021: 844) explained that it represents a high sense of happiness with work and a high desire to do and achieve, and is linked to the individual's mood and orientation, and uncontrollable feelings are generated towards work and that life is integrated with this work.

2-2- Green Innovation

- 1- **The concept**, explained by (Lin et al., 2016: 38), represents the process of development and improvement performed by the individual working in green production or service processes and is characterized by not negatively affecting the individual's life or the nature of the environment, so the outputs are environmentally friendly and provide economic and health returns. As (Ghayouratan & Hashamzade, 2016:222) indicated, it is creativity that contributes to improving performance (products and services) and works to reduce negative results. It is linked to products, processes, mechanisms, and programs that are all green and aim to save and conserve energy, prevent pollution, and work on green design. It contributes to meeting and preserving environmental requirements.
- 2- **Importance:** (Haslinda & Muruga 2016: 256) indicated that the importance is evident through what Green Innovation provides as a competitive advantage for organizations, whether in the local or global environment, enhancing the development of working individuals, increasing productivity or services, and an important factor in building and growth towards leadership. (Liu & Zhang, 2021: 2) confirmed that the importance is evident through contributing to improving the quality of performance and the ability to control polluting products to the environment while reducing waste and the possibility of recycling it and improving the mechanism of the environment of products to be environmentally friendly, as it contributes to maximizing economic and social benefits.
- 3- **Dimensions:** were adopted according to what was indicated by (Tseng et al., 2013: 73), which are (green design and green operations) and we will discuss this as follows: -

A- Green design: (Liu et al., 2017: 187) indicated that organizations seek to provide products and services designed in an environmentally friendly manner that does not have a negative impact, and it is an approved and continuous method to achieve environmental, health and safety goals as well as sustainability for this process so that it is an integrated life cycle without effects. (Komar, 2015: 45) explained that it is the process through which products or services are designed from raw materials free of harmful effects, whether on human health or the environment.

B- Green operations (Zhang & Zhu, 2019: 2) represent operations that are consistent with the term environmentally friendly in that they limit the ability to impact emissions and hazardous waste and recycle them to reduce the use of energy and raw materials, and this is what companies and organizations are working to apply in the current era. (Zaawin, 2022:20) pointed out that these highly efficient processes improve the mechanism of production or services and work to modify the organizational structure and method in line with the requirements of producing products and services that are environmentally friendly.

3- The practical aspect

"A questionnaire with a five-point Likert scale, from strongly disagreeing to strongly agreeing, was the main tool used to gather data for this project. The responses of the participants were assessed following the distribution of the questionnaire".

3-1- Using descriptive statistics to describe, diagnose, and look at data from study factors

Based on the feedback received from the sixteen-four observations, the researcher is now striving to ascertain the actuality, extent, and importance of the study variables (work passion, Green Innovation) within the Noor Al Kafeel Company. The researcher utilized the arithmetic mean of participants' responses to the paragraphs in each dimension, as well as their percentages

and standard deviation. Furthermore, the researcher took into account the relative significance (relative relevance) of each paragraph in the questionnaire, regardless of whether it belonged to the sub-level, dimension level, or main variable level under investigation. As the researcher relied on Likert's five-point scale to gather comments from the sample, the responses were limited to a range of five levels, as indicated in table (3).

Table 3. Likert ratings and level of availability

Resolution gradations	Relative importance
I don't quite agree	interest as low as 20%
I do not agree	From low to medium (40%-21%)
neutral	Average importance (60%-41%)
I agree	Intermediate to high interest (80%-61%)
Agree	High importance greater than 80%
Hypothetical mean = 15/5 = (3)	

Source: Akadiri O. P. (2011), Development of Multi-Criteria Approach for the Wolver Hampton, U. K.

1. Descriptive (analysis) of the job passion variable:

The table below shows a summary of the results of the job passion variable, It is evident that it attained a weighted average of (3.08) with a deviation of (0.834), while it achieved an agreement level of (61.68%), as the dimensions of the variable are centered towards neutrality. The results indicate that the level of awareness among employees in the company studied regarding job passion was average.

- (Harmonic passion) achieved a weighted average of (3.12) with a standard (deviation) of (0.825), while (the agreement) level reached (62.48%), as it occupied the (first) level in terms of the consistency of the answers of the selected sample.
- (Obsessive passion) achieved a weighted average of (3.04) with a standard (deviation) of (0.843), while (the agreement) level reached (60.88%), as it occupied the (second) level in terms of (the agreement) level of the answers of the selected sample.

Table (4) Descriptive criteria for the job passion variable

Phrases	Mean	Std. Deviation	Level of agreement	C.V	No.
First Dimension: Harmonious Passion					
I work with feelings of love and satisfaction in my work.	3.33	0.718	66.60%	%21.56	1
I feel pleasure in my work.	3.22	0.731	64.40%	22.70%	2
My work enhances my self-identity.	2.92	0.961	58.40%	32.91%	5
Harmonious passion develops loyalty among employees.	3.04	0.888	60.80%	29.21%	4
My work enhances the possibility of contributing to decision-making.	3.11	0.828	62.20%	26.62%	3
General Average	3.12	0.825	%62.48	%26.41	
The second dimension: Obsessive Passion					
My work allows me to do several activities.	2.99	0.838	59.80%	%28.03	3

My work takes up most of my time.	3.32	0.641	66.40%	19.31%	1
I cannot leave my work even for a specific time.	2.89	0.981	57.80%	33.94%	4
I use all my abilities to accomplish my work.	3.23	0.758	64.60%	23.47%	2
There has become a strong connection between the quality of my life and my work.	2.79	0.998	55.80%	35.77%	5
General Average	3.04	0.843	60.88%	27.70%	
Total job passion					
job passion	3.08	0.834	61.68%	27.05%	

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2- Descriptive (analysis) of the Green Innovation variable:

The table below shows a summary of the results of the Green Innovation variable, It is evident that it attained a weighted average of (3.01) with a deviation of (0.842), while it achieved an agreement level of (60.16%), as the dimensions of the variable are centered towards neutrality. The results indicate that the level of awareness among employees in the studied company of Green Innovation was average.

- (Green design) achieved a weighted average of (3.07) with a standard (deviation) of (0.781), while (the agreement) level reached (61.40%), as it occupied the (first) level in terms of the consistency of the answers of the selected sample.
- (Green operations) achieved a weighted average of (2.95) with a standard (deviation) of (0.903), while (the agreement) level reached (58.91%), as it occupied the (second) level in terms of (the agreement) level of the answers of the selected sample.

Table (5) Descriptive criteria for the Green Innovation variable

Phrases	Mean	Std. Deviation	Level of agreement	C.V	No.
First dimension: Green design					
The company produces environmentally friendly products continuously.	3.01	0.818	60.20%	%27.18	5
The environmental product produced by the company works well.	3.08	0.765	61.60%	24.84%	4
The standard design is adopted in the environmental product.	3.35	0.661	67.00%	19.73%	1
The environmental product produced by the company meets the requirements of environmental friendliness.	3.24	0.688	64.80%	21.23%	2
The environmental product is of high quality.	3.17	0.728	63.40%	22.97%	3
The company adopts scientific and practical specifications to improve the quality of the environmental product.	2.73	0.928	54.60%	33.99%	7
The company puts human health first in the design of the	2.91	0.878	58.20%	30.17%	6

environmental product.					
General Average	3.07	0.781	61.40%	25.44%	
Second Dimension: Green Operations					
The green process is an effective way to improve the green innovation mechanism.	2.65	1.018	53.00%	%38.42	7
The company uses non-toxic and non-polluting materials in the new product process.	2.87	0.941	57.40%	32.79%	5
The company uses modern methods in the production process of environmental products.	2.89	0.911	57.80%	31.52%	4
e company works on recycling waste scientifically.	2.77	0.988	55.40%	35.67%	6
When designing the new product, the company relies on international standards.	3.08	0.898	61.60%	29.16%	3
Rationalization and standardization of the requirements of the environmental product processes.	3.13	0.838	62.60%	26.77%	2
Green innovation processes target environmentally friendly outputs.	3.23	0.728	64.60%	22.54%	1
General Average	2.95	0.903	58.91%	30.66%	
Total green innovation					
green innovation	3.01	0.842	%60.16	%27.99	

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3-2- Evaluating the hypotheses regarding the correlation relationships between the research variables:

"This section of the research focuses on a statistical analysis that examines the correlation between the variables being studied" (job passion - the independent variable, with its two dimensions: harmonious passion, obsessive passion) - and the dependent variable, Green Innovation, are tested and analyzed. They are as described below:

Table (6) "Matrix of the correlation relationships for the research variables"

Green innovation	Dimensions of Functional Passion	"The value of the correlation coefficient and the level of significance"		"The intensity of the relationship"	"Direction of the relationship"	"the decision"
	Harmonious Passion	R	.7830	Strong	positive directive	Acceptance
	Sig.	0.000				
Obsessive Passion	R	0.751	Strong	positive directive	Acceptance	
	Sig.	0.000				
Functional Passion	R	0.873	Very Strong	positive directive	Acceptance	
	Sig.	0.000				
Percent	100%	.**Correlation is Significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)				

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The above table shows that the correlation between the two research variables (job passion - the independent variable, with its two dimensions: harmonious passion and obsessive passion) - and the dependent variable, Green Innovation, was positive and direct. This explains that increasing awareness among employees in the company under study, in turn, increases their Green Innovation through their behavior, which is reflected in Green Innovation at the level of the organization as a whole.

3-3- Confirmatory factor analysis of the research variables to verify the structural validity of the research scale with its variables, dimensions, and paragraphs

Structural equation modeling (confirmatory factor analysis method) will be used to verify this using the Amos. V program. 24). Through this procedure, the researcher aims to verify two issues: the dimensions express the variable, and its items are fair and statistically acceptable. Secondly, the data collected from the sample conforms to the hypothesized structural model of the measurement. The verification process is carried out through criteria that exceed or equal the saturation percentage of paragraphs to (0.40), in addition to the requirements for quality of conformity according to the following table:

Table 7: Indicators and rule of goodness of fit for structural modeling equation

	Indicators	Match quality rule
1	Goodness of Fit Index (GFI)	Greater than or equal to 0.90
2	Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)	Less than 0.05 or 0.08
3	Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	Greater than or equal to 0.95
4	The ratio between the values of X2 and the degrees of freedom df	Less than or equal to 3

Source: Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2017) "A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)," 2nd Ed. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage, p.289.

It is evident from the table and figure below that all items of the research variables (Functional Passion and Green innovation) exceeded their saturations (0.40), which means that they are statistically valid (Costello & Osborne, 2005), in addition to that the criteria for the quality of fit for the structural model were higher than the standards. This shows that the research variables are multi-dimensional and that the data collected from the sample are homogeneous with the assumed structural structure of the research variables, each variable separately. This confirms that the data drawn from the research sample conforms to the measurement model represented here by measuring each variable's research variables separately.

Table (8) Confirmatory factor analysis of study variables

Items	Path	The dimension	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
Confirmatory Factor Analysis of Functional Passion						
PH1	<---	Harmonious Passion	.795	.154	9.366	***
PH2	<---		.873	.152	9.894	***
PH3	<---		.865	.157	9.842	***
PH4	<---		.797	.148	9.382	***
PH5	<---		.585			
OP1	<---	Obsessive Passion	.776	.051	15.854	***
OP2	<---		.790	.050	16.387	***
OP3	<---		.819	.054	17.573	***
OP4	<---		.852	.050	19.105	***
OP5	<---		.902			

Confirmatory factor analysis of Green innovation						
GD1	<---	Green Design	.831			
GD2	<---		.817	.071	15.511	***
GD3	<---		.828	.067	15.864	***
GD4	<---		.872	.068	17.253	***
GD5	<---		.834	.069	16.045	***
GD6	<---		.809	.074	15.297	***
GD7	<---		.614	.073	10.459	***
GO1	<---	Green Operations	.821			
GO2	<---		.800	.063	14.598	***
GO3	<---		.828	.064	15.338	***
GO4	<---		.831	.060	15.425	***
GO5	<---		.814	.063	14.970	***
GO6	<---		.857	.060	16.168	***
GO7	<---		.832	.068	15.454	***

3-4- Results of testing the hypotheses of influence

"This paragraph will discuss the findings of evaluating the hypotheses of influence, which will be examined in a sequential manner":

The initial primary hypothesis (H1) is as follows: Green Innovation is significantly influenced by career passion, according to this hypothesis. In order to test this hypothesis, the structural equation was modeled in testing the influence relationship, "which means: Green Innovation is a real function of career passion and that any change in career passion will lead to enhancing Green Innovation, according to what was stated in the (table below) from the results of testing the (influence relationships), which showed that there is an influence relationship between career passion and Green Innovation, as the i(nfluence constant) reached (1.343), and the (slope) of the regression reached (0.94) directly, i.e.: when career passion increases by one unit, Green Innovation will increase by (0.94), in addition to the fact that career passion explains (87 percent) of the variance in (Green Innovation), while the remaining percentage of (13%) is due to other variables not included in the study, and it is significant based on the calculated (F) value (192.486), which is greater when compared to the (F) table of job passion, and the impact level value supports this result, which reached 0.000, is less than (the significance level), which the researcher assumed 0.05, and according to these results, the alternative hypothesis is accepted, and the null hypothesis is rejected at the level of this study, and this means: The equation for regression is as follows: the more employees' awareness of job passion increases, the additional it contributes to the enhancement of Green Innovation in(Noor Al Kafeel Company).":

$$y = a + bx$$

$$y = 1.343 + .94x$$

Figure (2) The independent variable's regression results, career passion, "and the dependent variable", Green Innovation.

Table (9) "The independent variable's regression results", career passion, and the dependent variable, Green Innovation

Dep. variable	path	Indep. variable	Estimates	القيمة الحرجة	Sig.	F-cal	F-table	Fixed effect	R Square
TSQ	<---	OC	0.94	8.541	***	192.486	3.82	1.343	.8710

1. **The first sub-hypothesis (H1-1):** This hypothesis states that there is a significant influence relationship between harmonious passion and Green Innovation. The results of the table below show that there is an influence relationship between harmonious passion and Green Innovation, as the influence constant reached (.7030). The slope of the regression reached (1.028) directly, i.e., when harmonious passion increases by one unit, Green Innovation will increase by (1.028), in addition to the fact that harmonious passion explains 61% of the variance in Green Innovation. In contrast, the remaining percentage (39%) is the result of other variables that were not incorporated into the study. The alternative hypothesis is accepted, and the null hypothesis is rejected at the level of this study, as evidenced by the calculated (F) value (257.18), which is higher than the tabular (F) value of (3.82). The significance level value, which reached (0.000), is less than the significance level that the researcher assumed (0.05).: The more the workers' awareness of the harmonious passion among the workers increases, the more it contributes to enhancing Green Innovation in Noor Al Kafeel Company, and "the regression equation is as follows":

$$y = a + bx$$

$$y = 1.028 + .703x$$

Table (10) "Regression model between" Harmonious Passion and Green Innovation

Model	Non-standard transactions		standard transactions	F-cal	F-table	R Square	Sig.
	Beta coefficient	Standard error	Beta				
1	Constant	1.028	.137	257.18	3.82	0.61	.000
	Harmonic Passion	.7030	.044				

Find developed by the academic using data from SPSS.26

Figure (3) Regression model between harmonious passion and Green Innovation

2- **"The second sub-hypothesis:** This hypothesis posits that there is a substantial relationship between Green Innovation and acquisitive fervor. The table below demonstrates that there is a correlation between Green Innovation and acquisitive passion, as the influence constant is (1.055). The regression slope was directly attained at .7030, i.e., when acquisitive passion increases by one unit, Green Innovation will increase by an amount of (.7030), in addition to the fact that acquisitive passion explains (56%) of the variance in Green Innovation. "Conversely, the study did not investigate the factors that account for the remaining proportion (44%) of the total. The alternative hypothesis is supported, and the null hypothesis is rejected in this study, as indicated by the calculated (F) value (209.34), which exceeds the tabular (F) value of (3.82). The obtained significance level value of 0.000 is lower than the assumed significance level of 0.05 by the researcher. The regression equation states that an increase in the availability and awareness of obsessive passion among workers leads to a bigger contribution to increasing Green Innovation in Noor Al Kafeel Company".

$$y = a + bx$$

$$y = 1.055 + .703x$$

Table (11) "Regression model between" obsessive passion and Green Innovation

Model	Non-standard transactions		standard transactions	F-cal	F-table	R Square	Sig.
	Beta coefficient	Standard error	Beta				
1	Constant	1.055	.149	209.34	3.82	0.56	.000
	obsessive passion	.703	.049				

Find developed by the academic using data from SPSS.26

Figure (4) Regression model between obsessive passion and Green Innovation

4- "Conclusions and Recommendations"

4-1- Conclusions:

"The following are the most significant conclusions that the researcher arrived at by translating the applied and statistical results he obtained through the practical aspect":

A. The average level of interest and cognizance in the practices of job passion (harmonious passion, obsessive passion) among employees at Noor Al Kafeel Company was indicated by the neutral or agreeable responses of the majority of the respondents to the majority of the paragraphs.

B. The availability of Green Innovation practices at Noor Al Kafeel Company was average, as the majority of the study sample's responses were neutral. This suggests that creativity practices require improvement.

C. The analysis of the correlation relationships between job passion and Green Innovation reveals that they were high, direct, and significant. This suggests that the greater the awareness of job passion among employees at Noor Al Kafeel Company, the more it contributed to the enhancement of Green Innovation.

D. The analysis of the effect between harmonious passion and Green Innovation reveals that it was high, direct, and significant. This suggests that the awareness of harmonious passion among employees at Noor Al Kafeel Company increased as a result of their awareness of the existence of feelings of love and satisfaction in their work, the existence of self-identity in their work, and their feeling of enjoyment in their work. Additionally, they were aware that their work enhanced the possibility of contributing to making decisions, whenever it led to enhancing Green Innovation.

E. The impact between obsessive passion and Green Innovation was high, direct, and significant, as evidenced by the analysis. This suggests that the more employees at Noor Al Kafeel Company are aware of the existence of obsessive passion, the more they are able to enhance Green Innovation. This is due to the fact that employees are aware of the strong link between the quality of their lives and their work, the exploitation of all of their capabilities in completing their work, and the feeling that their work takes up the majority of their time. Additionally, they are aware that their work allows them to engage in diverse activities.

4-2- recommendations

The recommendations were established during the research phase, which involved the collection of data, the evaluation of previous studies, and the application aspect and the review of the results during the visit to Noor Al Kafeel Company. The recommendations are as follows:

1. Building an organizational culture that supports green passion and creativity:

- Vision and mission: Guarantee that the organization's vision and mission specify explicit objectives concerning environmental responsibility and sustainability.
- Shared values: Encourage the development of values that promote environmental protection and innovation, including critical thinking, cooperation, respect, and responsibility.
- Leadership: Motivate leaders to serve as role models by promoting the adoption of sustainable practices and offering assistance to green initiatives.
- Communication: Effectively communicate with employees regarding the company's environmental accomplishments and the significance of sustainability.

2. Providing a work environment that stimulates creativity:

- Creative spaces: Creating adaptable workspaces that foster creativity, such as indoor gardens or brainstorming chambers.
- Technology and tools: Providing the requisite technology and tools to facilitate the development of innovative ideas, including simulation and design programs.
- Training and Development: Offering workshops and seminars and encouraging employees to participate in specialized training programs in the fields of sustainability and creativity.
- Appreciation and recognition: Commending employees who propose sustainable initiatives and innovative ideas.

3. Encouraging participation and collaboration:

- Multidisciplinary teams: Establishing multidisciplinary work teams that consist of employees from various departments to facilitate the exchange of ideas and knowledge.
- Volunteer programs: Coordinating volunteer programs that emphasize environmental concerns, including the planting of trees or the cleansing of beaches.
- Internal social networks: Establishing an internal social networking platform that enables employees to exchange ideas and engage in discussions regarding environmental issues.

4. Linking performance to sustainability:

- Key performance indicators: Establishing a connection between environmental accomplishments and a portion of employees' key performance indicators.
- Financial and non-financial incentives: Offering financial and non-financial incentives to employees who assist in the attainment of the organization's environmental objectives.

5. Investing in research and development:

- Research projects: Facilitating research projects that concentrate on the creation of environmentally favorable products and services.
- Strategic partnerships: Forming partnerships with universities and research institutions to create innovative solutions to environmental challenges.

6. Continuous measurement and evaluation:

- Key performance indicators: Establishing key performance indicators to assess advancements in the fields of sustainability and innovation.

- Feedback: Providing employees with consistent feedback on their sustainability-related performance.

The References:

1. Birkeland, I. & Buch, R. (2015). The dualistic model of passion for work: Discriminate and predictive validity with work engagement and workaholism, *Motiv Emot Journal*, 39: 392–408.
2. Fu, Y., Tietz, M. A., & Delmar, F. 2022. Obsessive passion and the venture team: When co-founders join, and when they don't. *Journal of Business Venturing*, (37) 4.
3. Ghayourvatan, Nasrin & Hashemzade, Gholamreza (2016) Explaining the Relationship between the Role of Green Innovation on the Brand and its Impact on Organizational Performance (Case Study: Iran Khodro), *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF HUMANITIES AND CULTURAL STUDIES*.
4. Haslinda M. & Muruga C. (2016). Malaysian SMEs Development: Future and Challenges on Going Green. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* ,254 – 262.
5. Ho, V. T., Garg, S., & Rogelberg, S. G. 2021. Passion contagion at work: Investigating formal and informal social influences on work passion. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 131-145.
6. Kumar, P., & Ghodeswar, B.M. (2015). Factors affecting consumers' green product purchase decisions. *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*.
7. Lin, Ru-Jen, Chen, Rong-Huei & Ho, Thao-Minh (2013) Market Demand, Green Innovation, and Firm Performance: Evidence From Hybrid Vehicle Industry, *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, Vol. 21.
8. Liu, M., & Zhang, H. (2021). "Green technology innovation, media attention and enterprise performance". In *E3S Web of Conferences*, Vol. (2)67, EDP Sciences.p1-49.
9. Liu, Y., Zhu, Q., & Seuring, S. (2017). Linking capabilities to green operations strategies: The moderating role of corporate environmental proactivity. *International Journal of Production Economics*, pp, 182-195
10. Newman, A., Obschonka, M., Moeller, J., & Chandan, G. G. (2021). Entrepreneurial passion: A review, synthesis, and agenda for future research. *Applied Psychology*, 70(2), 816-860.
11. Pathak, D., & Srivastava, S. 2020. Journey from passion to satisfaction: roles of belongingness and psychological empowerment. *International Journal of Sociology and Social Policy*, 40(3/4): 321-341.
12. Pollack, J. M., Ho, V. T., O'Boyle, E. H., & Kirkman, B. L. (2020). Passion at work: A meta-analysis of individual work outcomes. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 41(4), 311-331.
13. Tolentino, L. R., Lajom, J. A. L., Sibunruang, H., & Garcia, P. R. J. M. 2022. The bright side of loving your work: Optimism as a mediating mechanism between work passion and employee outcomes. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 194.
14. Tseng, Ming-Lang and Wang, Ray and Chiu, Anthony S.F.and Geng, Yong and Lin, Yuan Hsu,2013" Improving performance of green innovation practices under uncertainty", *Journal of Cleaner Production*
15. Vallerand, R. J., & Houliort, N. (Eds.). (2019). *Passion for work: Theory, research, and applications*. Oxford University Press
16. Zawawi, W. (2022). Analysis of the environmental factors affecting green innovation: An applied study on a sample of industrial enterprises - western Algeria. *Journal of Economic Additions*, 6(1).